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MULTICOMPONENT REACTIONS AND RECENT ADVANCES IN THE APPLICATIONS OF OXADIAZOLES FROM 2017-18: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

1,3,4-Oxadiazole is a thermally stable and neutral Heteroaromatic molecule having a wide variety of uses, particularly as biologically active compounds in medicine, agriculture, dye stuffs, UV absorbing and fluorescent materials, heat resistant polymers and scintillators. Oxadiazoles and their analogues can be considered as simple five membered heterocycles possessing one oxygen and two nitrogen atoms¹⁻⁶. The oxadiazole exists in different isomeric forms such as 1,3,4- oxadiazole, 1,2,5-oxadiazole, 1,2,4-oxadiazole, and 1,2,3-oxadiazole, out of which 1,3,4-Oxadiazole is a thermally stable neutral aromatic molecule and its estimated resonance energy is 167.4 kJ/mol. particularly, aryl group at position 2 increases the thermal stability of 1,3,4-oxadiazole. The ring is stable to heat, a property which has been exploited in the production of heat-resistant poly-1,3,4-oxadiazoles. UV spectra of substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles are similar to those of substituted benzenes, particularly in the case of 2-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles⁷⁻¹⁸ (λ_{max} in ethanol = 247.5 nm, $\log \epsilon$ 4.26).

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INTRODUCTION

The first monosubstituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were reported in 1955 by two independent laboratories. Studies on 1,3,4-oxadiazoles and its cation indicates a maximum positive charge on the second position. Alkyl and aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles are neutral compounds and 2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles are weakly basic¹⁹⁻²⁶. 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have a relatively low electron density at carbon (position 2 and 5) and relatively high electron density at nitrogen (position 3 and 4). Consequently the major reactions performed by nucleophilic attack at carbon, followed by ring cleavage and electrophilic attack at nitrogen atom. The attack of a nucleophile at carbon 2 leads either to nucleophilic displacement or ring cleavage. The most frequently encountered result of the reaction of a 1,3,4-oxadiazole with a nucleophile is the ring opening reaction which leads to hydrazine derivatives. Oxadiazole is an important heterocyclic ring present in variety of biologically active molecules inclusive of fungicidal, bactericidal, anticancer, antitubercular activities, etc. Oxadiazole moiety is derived from furan by replacing two $-CH=$ group with 2 pyrimidine typed nitrogen ($-N=$). So there should be possibility of four oxadiazole isomers reliant on the nitrogen atom position in the ring. 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have considerable interest in different areas such as medicinal, pesticide, polymer and material science²⁷⁻³⁴.

DIFFERENT METHODS OF REACTIONS

Malhotra M et al³⁵ (2017) Were reported the synthesis, antimicrobial and antioxidant evaluation of a series of 1,3,4 substituted oxadiazole derivatives. Antimicrobial evaluation revealed that eighteen compounds were able to display variable growth inhibitory effects on the tested Gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, Gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* and fungal strains *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*.

Salahuddin et al³⁶ (2017) Were reported the development of oxadiazole bearing benzimidazole system has new potentially active antibacterial and antifungal agents. The results of in vitro antimicrobial activities showed that the compounds having deactivating group (electron withdrawing group like NO_2 , Br and Cl) and weakly activating group i.e., CH_3 group were the most active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The antifungal activity confirmed that the compound having Cl , NO_2 , Br and methyl group in the oxadiazole system is the most potent against *A. flavus* and *C. albicans* respectively.

Zhou L et al³⁷ (2017) were reported a series of pyridinium-tailored 5-trifluoromethylpyrazoles containing 1,3, 4-oxadiazole moieties were constructed through coupling key pharmaceutical fragments of pyridinium, pyrazole, and 1,3,4-oxadiazole scaffolds in single molecular architecture.

Gul S et al³⁸ (2017) were reported the series of 2-[[5-alkyl/aralkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl] thio]-N-[4-(4 morpholinyl) phenyl] acetamides (6a-m) were prepared by converting different aryl/aralkyl organic acids (1a-m) successively into corresponding esters (2a-m), hydrazides (3a-m) and 5-aryl/aralkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiols (4a-m).

Husain A et al³⁹ (2017) were reported newly synthesized compounds, 2-(biphenyl-4-ylmethyl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (6c) emerged as the most potent NSAID compound exhibiting the highest anti-inflammatory activity (72.87 % inhibition) and analgesic activity (65.24%) along with the least severity index on gastric mucosa (0.20).

Parth et Al⁴⁰ (2017) reported a series of 2, 5-disubstituted 1, 3, 4-Oxadiazole derivatives (4A-4G) have been synthesized with the help of different aromatic benzaldehyde and final compounds were characterized by FT-IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectroscopy. The anticancer study was investigated against Ehrlich Ascites Carcinoma (EAC) bearing albino mice.

Ali Souldozi et al⁴¹ (2017) reported a new series of (5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)(pyridin-2-yl)methanol derivatives (4a-4d) in fairly high yields and evaluated the antimicrobial activity of these derivatives against the microorganisms.

Neeraj Kumar Fuloria et al⁴² (2017) reported a new series of 2-(4-Chloro-3,5- dimethyl phenoxy) acetohydrazide, prepared from ethyl 2-(4-chloro-3,5-dimethylphenoxy)acetate, when cyclized with aromatic acids offered 2-((4-chloro-3,5-dimethylphenoxy)methyl)-5-(aryl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (4a-f).

Jafari et al⁴³ (2017) reported a new series of Nitro-furanoxadiazole compound easily obtained by reacting N-acylhydrazone with acetic anhydride in moderate yield.

Andrews et al⁴⁴ (2018) reported a series of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenyl pyrimidin-2(1H)-one derivatives have been synthesized by changing various substituted benzaldehydes. Among the synthesized derivatives, some of the derivatives showed very good inhibition against bacteria.

Mohan et al⁴⁵ (2018) reported a designed novel small molecule inhibitors that target NF- κ B activation is of prime important in the treatment of several cancers. He reported the synthesis of series of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, investigated their anticancer potential against HCC cells, and identified 2-(3-chlorobenzo[b]thiophen-2-yl)-5-(3-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (CMO) as the lead compound.

Azhar HG et al⁴⁶ (2018) reported a series of new ligand 2,2'-((1Z,2Z)-ethane-1,2-diylidenebis((2Z)hydrazin-1-yl-2-ylidene-1,3,4-oxadiazole-5,2-diyl))diphenol and its Cr(III), Co(III) and Ni(II) complexes were synthesized. The ligand and its complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, conductance measurements, as well as spectroscopy (1H NMR, IR, mass), magnetic susceptibility. A new ligand and its complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against two kinds of strains Escherichia coli (gram negative bacterial strains) and staphylococcus aureus (gram positive bacteria strains) using the agar disk diffusion method.

Prasad et al⁴⁷ (2018) reported a new series of 1-phenyl-3-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-1H-pyrazole derivatives as a series of novel 1,3,4-oxadiazoles (7a-7h) through iodine-catalyzed oxidative cyclization of the hydrazone derivatives.

CONCLUSION

The present review highlights that the 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety as a template for the development of newer therapeutic agents. Modified 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety displayed the various synthetic methods and valuable biological activities.

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